

Chemistry-Specific Catalogue: DFG-Checklist

The present questionnaire is a checklist issued by the German Research Foundation (DFG), enriched with chemistry-specific content and supplemented with necessary questions for better understanding and completeness. The DFG checklist must be submitted with your application and at the project's completion and is intended to assist you in structuring your data management. If you have any questions, please contact the central Research Data Management (RDM) team at your university or research institution, or reach out to NFDI4Chem at helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de.

The following questions are for describing chemical datasets generated and/or used in the project. The definition of what constitutes a dataset is an important conceptual decision that must be made individually for each institute or project. Choose a logical unit of your research data as a dataset, to which the same information regarding methodology, technology, accessibility, etc., applies. This can be, for example, a molecule, synthesis steps, the employed analysis method, similar simulation calculations, etc.

Categorising data into datasets helps assess the value of the data in terms of potential reuse and subsequent archiving. Since all questions must be answered for each individual dataset, an overly granular structure is not practical. Some aspects of data handling can be generalised and documented through accompanying policies. The preferred approach to managing data is typically communicated at the beginning of a project, either verbally or in writing, and is conveyed to subsequent doctoral candidates during their onboarding. An example of such a policy can be found from the Daumann Group at: <https://www.bioac.hhu.de/bioinorganic-chemistry/team-1-1>

You can use this catalogue of questions as a text document for support or in the Research Data Management Organizer (RDMO) tool provided for data management plans. This offers you the opportunity to collaborate with project partners, colleagues, NFDI4Chem, RDMO also offers you the following advantages:

- RDMO supports your data management over the entire life of the project.
- RDMO can compile all relevant planning data and data management tasks over the entire life cycle of the research data.
- The catalogue can be used in German or English, depending on your preference.
- Various DMP templates are offered.
- RDMO can automatically distribute tasks to project members
- RDMO has an import/export function and offers various formats for download.

Section: Data Description

Question Set: Content Data Description

Question: How does your project generate new data?

Options:

- Experimental data on synthesis
- Simulation data oder quantum mechanical calculations (DFT, MM, Docking etc)
- Spectroscopic data
- Microscopic data (e.g. SEM, TEM, ...)
- Crystallographic data
- Voltammetric data
- Laboratory / field observation data (e.g. cohort questionnaires)
- Tables
- Textual data
- Image data
- Other data: FREETEXT

Question: How does your project generate new data?

Help:

Research data is typically generated in every research project. Here, you should reflect upon and describe the ways in which you generate research data. The methods of data generation may vary depending on your specific chemical subdiscipline. Consider the methods and tools you use.

Options:

- Chemical experiments
- Analytical determinations
- Observations (through human observation, instruments, or sensors)
- Calculations, models, or simulations
- Derivation or compilation from other data sources
- Visualisations
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Question: Is existing data reused?

Help:

In chemistry, existing data are often reused. The most commonly used data include crystal structures and analytical results used for comparing newly generated data. Existing data can also serve as the foundation for a new project or be used for specific parts of the project. This is often the case with data generated within research groups. Check to see if you can use any existing data for your project.

Possible databases:

- Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (<https://icsd.fiz-karlsruhe.de/search/basic.xhtml;jsessionid=3E38CBFD6DABF1686D0F84DBFDA12FED>)
- Materials Project (<https://materialsproject.org/>)
- Chemotion Repository (<https://www.chemotion-repository.net/welcome>)

Additionally, NFDI4Chem offers a Search Service (<https://search.nfdi4chem.de/>) that allows simultaneous searches across multiple chemistry-specific repositories.

Options:

- Experimental data for synthesis (e.g., NMR, IR, MS)
- Simulation data
- Spectroscopic data
- Microscopic data (e.g., SEM, TEM, ...)
- Crystallographic data
- Voltammetric data
- Image data
- Other data [FREETEXT]

Question Set: Technical Data Description

Question: Which data types (in terms of data formats) arise in your project?

Help:

Different devices may produce various data formats, some of which may not be compatible with each other. Additionally, some device manufacturers use proprietary data formats. When choosing a data format, it is advisable to use standardised, non-proprietary formats that are commonly used in chemistry. Raw data should also be retained in the original file format if the file size allows.

Options:

- JCAMP-DX
- AnIML
- netCDF
- CSV
- ASCII
- ISA
- UDM
- ADF
- mzML
- ANDI-MS
- nmrML
- NMReDATA
- Bruker FID
- mnova
- Bruker OPUS
- Perkin Elmer

- Thermofisher Grams
- pdf
- txt
- docx
- proprietary formats from equipment manufacturers: [FREETEXT]
- Other text processing formats: [FREETEXT]
- Other formats for data analysis and processing: [FREETEXT]
- Other formats for images, photos, and videos: [FREETEXT]
- Self-developed formats: [FREETEXT]
- Other data formats: [FREETEXT]

Question: And in what way are they further processed?

Help:

The following questions may help: What characterisation/analysis methods do you use? What are the steps involved in your approach? You may have recorded the steps in your laboratory notebook, if you use one. In a future version of the checklist, you will be able to link the steps to sample identifiers and generate an overview.

Option:

FREETEXT RESPONSE

Question: To what extent do these arise or what is the anticipated data volume?

Options:

- Less than 1 GB
- Between 1 GB and 1 TB
- Between 1 TB and 100 TB
- More than 100 TB
- Not yet determined

Section: Documentation and Data Quality

Question Set: Documentation

Question: What approaches are being taken to describe the data in a comprehensible manner (such as the use of available metadata, documentation standards or ontologies)?

Help:

In chemistry, one of the most common methods for documenting data is the laboratory notebook, either electronic or paper-based. The information is often recorded in a structured way as metadata. The metadata fields are partly determined by the lab notebook, partly defined by the user. For the choice of the fields it is recommended to follow the scheme of the target repository (examples: Chemotion <https://www.chemotion-repository.net/welcome>, Crystallography Open Database <https://www.crystallography.net/cod/>) or qualified recommendations, such as

- NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base (https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/metadata/?highlight=michi#minimum-information-for-chemical-investigations-michi)
- schema.org (<https://schema.org/MolecularEntity>)
- Subject- and application-specific initiatives such as nmrML (<https://nmrml.org/>)

If you need further assistance, please contact the NFDI4Chem Helpdesk.

Options:

- The following electronic laboratory notebook with predefined metadata is used: [FREETEXT]
- An electronic or paper-based laboratory notebook is used, in which the following metadata are documented: [FREETEXT] with multiple input options
- No laboratory notebook is used, but the following metadata are captured: [FREETEXT] with multiple input options

Question: Which digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?

Help:

The use of digital methods and tools enables chemists to collect, analyse, interpret, and derive new scientific insights from experimental data. To make these insights usable by others, it is important to document the software, equipment, etc. Also, please refer back to the question regarding data formats.

Options:

- Code in the programming language: Python
- Code in the programming language: R
- Code in the programming language: C/C++
- Software: Origin
- Software: spreadsheet program (LibreOffice, Excel)

- Software: document editor (LibreOffice, Word)
- Software: LaTeX editor (TeXWorks, TeXMaker...)
- Software: Matlab
- Software: MNova
- Software: Bruker Topspin NMR
- Software: Thermo Fisher Excalibur for mass spectrometry
- Software: Thermo Fisher TraceFinder
- Software: Sciex Analyst / MultiQuant
- Software: Agilent MassHunter
- Software: ChemDraw
- Software: Citation software (Zotero, Citavi, Reference Manager, EndNote, MZmine 2)
- Software: Metlin XCMS
- Software: Gaussian
- Software: AmberTools Amber
- Software: JASCO Spectra Manager
- Software: Bruker OPUS
- Software: Agilent ChemStation
- Software: FullProf
- Software: CTM4XAS
- Software: Crispy
- Software: Wien2K
- Software: ACD Labs
- Software: OpenEye
- Software: Thermo Fisher Chromelon
- Software: PerkinElmer UV WinLab
- Software: Autodesk Inventor
- Software: Shimadzu LabSolutions
- Software: Leica LAS X
- Software: Spectragryph
- Software: CasaXPS Self-developed software: [FREETEXT]
- Other software: [FREETEXT]
- Image editing: Adobe Illustrator
- Other digital methods: [FREETEXT]
- Other tools: [FREETEXT]

Question Set: Data Quality

Question: What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality?

Help:

Various measures are implemented in chemistry to ensure data quality. One of the most well-known methods is the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP), which many research groups define for their characterisation/analysis methods and workflows.

Options:

- Use of calibration methods
- Repetition of measurements
- Data capture
- Validation of data input and output
- Standardisation of procedures and protocols through careful experiment planning and documentation of all steps
- Adherence to Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)
- Documentation of relevant parameters and metadata
- Calibration of measuring instruments
- Conducting measurements according to standards
- Use of predefined quality criteria. These include [FREETEXT]
- Use of a controlled vocabulary. This includes [FREETEXT]
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Question: Are quality controls in place and if so, how do they operate?

Help:

Quality controls depend on various factors, such as the chemistry subfield and structures within the institute or project. It is important that quality control is independent of the measures taken and relates to the product "data." Examples would include: peer review by a colleague, supervisor, data steward, etc. Or through a tool, checksums, etc. Also, specify the timing of the quality control(s).

Option:

- Data collection - computerised data collection (standardised, verified, consistent)
- Data collection - Calibration of instruments (accuracy/scale)
- Data collection - standardised methods and protocols (with clear instructions)
- Data collection - multiple measurements, observations or samples
- Data collection - expert review
- Data verification - double checking of data and outlier values
- Data verification - correction of errors made during data entry
- Data verification - peer review
- Data verification - Statistical analyses such as frequencies, mean values, dispersion or clustering to detect errors and anomalous values
- Data verification - comparison of random data with original data
- Data verification - checking for duplicate entries
- Data verification - checking for completeness
- Digitisation and data entry - Accompanying notes and documentation on the data

- Digitisation and data entry - Detailed labelling of variable and data set names
- Digitisation and data entry - Controlled vocabularies, code lists and selection lists to minimise manual data entry
- Digitisation and data entry - Validation rules or input masks
- Digitisation and data entry - Use of a specially developed database structure to organise data/files
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Section: Storage and Technical Security During the Project

Question Set: Data Storage During the Project

Question: How is the data to be stored and archived throughout the project duration?

Help:

This question deals with storage of "hot data" during the period when you are actively working with the data. Where and how you store research data depends on your local working routines and systems and from the actors who need access to the data (possibly external partners) Advantages and disadvantages of different storage media can be found at [forschungsdaten.info](https://www.forschungsdaten.info). In order to prevent data loss, it is also recommended to follow the 3-2-1 rule for data storage: 3 copies of the data, among them 2 on different media types, and 1 offline copy.

(<https://www.forschungsdaten.info/themen/speichern-und-rechnen/datenspeicherung-und-die-lebensdauer-von-datentraegern/>).

Options:

- Cloud solution: [FREETEXT]
- GitHub/GitLab
- Central solution (e.g., network drives and automatic data mirroring, Own server infrastructure at the institute, etc.)
- Decentralized solution (e.g., servers in the data center of your university or research institution)
- Own computer/laptop hard drive
- External hard drives
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Question: How are the generated or existing physical samples linked to the data during the project's duration?

Help:

In addition to proper documentation, linking physical samples to experimental data plays a crucial role in ensuring reproducibility, quality assurance, and analysis of research results. The linking process depends on the targets and requirements of a project, especially if there are no specific plans from your institution.

Options:

- Linking through the following naming convention: [FREETEXT]
- Linking through the following metadata in the laboratory notebook: [FREETEXT]
- Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS)
- Following cheminformatics tools: [FREETEXT]
- Barcodes and the following identification methods: [FREETEXT]
- Following sample databases: [FREETEXT]
- Databases: [FREETEXT]
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Question Set: Technical Data Security During the Project

Question: What is in place to secure sensitive data throughout the project duration (access and usage rights)?

Help:

When discussing sensitive data in chemistry, these data are typically not personal data. Sensitive data often arise in projects with industrial collaborations. Data may become sensitive during a project when considerations about patenting arise. Access and usage rights are then documented in confidentiality agreements, known as Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs). Explain here how you regulate access, especially if you have restrictions, and mention the tools you use. Also, consider the next question where you can go into more detail about the reasons for these restrictions. If you have questions about ethical, legal, and social aspects, the ELSA section (Link: <https://www.nfdi.de/section-elsa/>) can support you.

Option:

[FREETEXTANSWER]

Section: Legal obligations and conditions

Question: What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project?

Help:

If you're going to handle personal data, please note it here. The handling of personal data is regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In addition, there are data protection laws in various federal states. Please find out in advance. If you have any questions about personal data and its security, please contact the data protection officer at your university or research institution. Special conditions may arise from confidentiality agreements with industrial collaborations or potential patenting. Briefly explain what these special conditions entail.

Option:

[FREETEXT ANSWER]

Question Set: Restrictions on Publication

Question: Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?

Help:

Many researchers share their data at the end of a project. There are many reasons to do that, such as to guarantee reproducibility and traceability of workflows and formats. Many publishers also expect published data to accompany the text publication. For details, see "The current landscape of author guidelines in chemistry through the lens of research data sharing" (<https://doi.org/10.1515/pac-2022-1001>).

However, there may be reasons against (direct) data publication. These may include the commercial or industrial exploitation of data, or confidentiality related to security concerns.

In case that just the priority of a discovery needs to be protected, one possible solution is a data publication with a so-called embargo or retention period, data publication is possible. This requires the data to be already completely analysed and prepared, but allows to offer them to the public audience at a later timepoint of your wish.

Further information can be found in the Code of Good Scientific Practice, namely within Guideline 13 "Public Access to Research Results" <https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/kodex/herstellung-von-offentlichem-zugang-zu-forschungsergebnissen/>

Options:

- No, there are no restrictions. The data will be published with the text publication.
- No, there are no restrictions. The data will be published no later than at the end of the project.
- Yes, the data are subject to a confidentiality agreement and can only be published after years [FREETEXT].
- Yes, publishing the data would violate the intellectual property rights of third parties.
- Yes, the data cannot be published due to the following legal aspects: [FREETEXT]
- Yes, personal data is being used.

Question Set: Scientific Specifics

Question: Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?

Help:

In addition to general scientific codices, there are also chemistry-specific codices. If you are not familiar with these, the DFG's page on scientific integrity (<https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/>) can help. Here, you will find references to laws, chemistry-specific commenting on guidelines and explanations, as well as case examples.

Options:

- Code "Guidelines for Ensuring Good Scientific Practice"
- Guideline for Research Data Management at your university or research institution
- Open Access Policy at your university or research institution
- Documentation of research results in experimental chemistry
- Quality assurance in experimental chemistry
- Use of chemistry-specific repositories
- Handling research software - case examples
- Ethical principles in chemistry
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Question Set: Legal Restrictions

Question: What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues?

Help:

Legal aspects need to be considered when dealing with a dataset. Whether your data are subject to copyright protection depends, among other things, on their originality. You can find information on this in the "Copyright Protection of Research Data" factsheet (https://www.rwth-aachen.de/global/show_document.asp?id=aaaaaaaaavchxo) or under "Copyright and Licensing for Research Data" (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5243232>). Answers to legal questions about Open Science can be found in the book "Legal Issues in Open Science" by Kreutzer and Lahmann (<https://doi.org/10.15460/HUP.211>).

Option:

[FREETEXT ANSWER]

Section: Data exchange and long-term data accessibility

Question Set: Reuse

Question: Which data sets are especially suitable for use in other contexts?

Help:

Due to the fundamental role of chemistry in other fields, please consider whether your data can be reused.

Options:

- Yes, the data can be potentially reused by researchers in the following discipline:
[FREETEXT]
- Yes, the data can be reused for training purposes.
- Yes, my research is socially relevant, and the data can be reused by the public.
- Yes, because [FREETEXT]
- No, I cannot envision a reuse scenario for the data.
- No, because [FREETEXT]

Question: Which criteria are used to select research data to make it available for subsequent use by others?

Options:

- Documentation duty according to Good Scientific Practice (generally 10 years)
- Potential reuse for reproduction or verification of research results
- Basis for further research (especially research data with high reuse relevance)
- Uniqueness (data cannot be reproduced)
- Cost/effort (data production is very laborious or expensive)
- Belonging to a scientific text publication
- Better traceability of the associated text publication
- High data quality
- High novelty of the data
- Other: [FREETEXT]

Question: When is the research data available for use by third parties?

Help:

According to the DFG's "Guidelines for Research Data Management"

(https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/grundlagen_dfg_foerderung/forschungsdaten/leitlinien_forschungsdaten.pdf), research data should be made available as soon as possible and, in the best case, follow the FAIR principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Re-Usability (<https://force11.org/info/guiding-principles-for-findable-accessible-interoperable-and-re-usable-data-publishing-version-b1-0/>). The importance of data publication is also emphasised in Guideline 13 of the Code of Good Scientific Practice "Public Access to Research Results" (<https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/kodex/herstellung-von-offentlichem-zugang-zu-forschungsergebnissen/>). It points to discipline-specific practices.

For the publication of research data, it is recommended to use discipline-specific repositories. Recommended directories to find a suitable repository include:

- NFDI4Chem Search Service (<https://search.nfdi4chem.de/>)
- Re3data.org (<https://www.re3data.org/>)
- FAIRSharing.org (<https://fairsharing.org/>)

Options:

- Most likely during the project
- Directly after the end of the project
- 1 year after the end of the project
- 2 years after the end of the project
- 5 years after the end of the project
- 10 years after the end of the project
- Following years after the end of the project: [FREETEXT]
- The dataset will not be usable for third parties. [FREETEXT]

Question Set: Archiving

Question: How do you archive your data and in which suitable infrastructure?

Help:

In accordance with good scientific practice, research data must generally be stored for 10 years. (see Guideline 17 of the Code of Good Scientific Practice "Archiving" (<https://wissenschaftliche-integritaet.de/kodex/archivierung/>))

To ensure that the data remains available and retrievable, it must also be maintained beyond the project. If you archive the data in a data centre or repository, the responsibility is usually assumed by the operators. Please check or clarify the responsibilities in advance. The archiving service of your university/research institution may be free of charge for members and often guarantees secure storage of the data in accordance with the requirements of good scientific practice. Archiving includes metadata, documentation and any relevant code/software.

Options:

- Archive service of your university or research institution
- Other: FREITEXT

Question: Are embargo periods to be observed? If so, how long are they?

Help:

As mentioned above, an embargo or embargo period allows the data to be published at a later date. Whether the selected repository offers such an embargo/locking period must be determined in advance.

Options:

[FREETEXT]

Question: How are the physical samples archived, and how are data linked to the physical samples?

Help:

In chemistry, long-term storage of physical samples is often done in the laboratory itself by means of refrigerators and freezers. An alternative is provided by the central service ComPlat at KIT, which offers a central storage of chemical substances (<https://www.ioc.kit.edu/braese/1020.php>).

Linking data and physical samples is important for reproducibility and data quality, both during the project and after its end. For that purpose a sample database or inventory system, such as FindMolecule (<https://findmolecule.com/>) may help.

Options:

[FREETEXT]

Section: Responsibilities and Resources

Question Set: Responsibilities

Question: Who is responsible for the appropriate handling of research data (description of roles and responsibilities within the project)?

Help:

We recommend providing individuals in the following format: Title; First Name, Last Name; ORCID (if available); Professional Position; Institute; Contact Information; Role in the Project.

Option:

[FREETEXT]

Question: Who is responsible for curating the data after the project's duration?

Help:

We recommend providing individuals in the following format: Title; First Name, Last Name; ORCID (if available); Professional Position; Institute; Contact Information; Role in the Project.

Option:

[FREETEXT]

Question Set: Resources

Question: What resources (costs, time, or other) are required to implement appropriate research data management in the project?

Help:

This can include technical or IT resources as well as expertise, which may be provided by data management or IT experts. You can provide more detailed information about each item if necessary.

Options:

- Infrastructure resource: RDMO
- Infrastructure resource: File server
- Infrastructure resource: Virtual servers
- Infrastructure resource: GitLab
- Infrastructure resource: Cloud solution
- Infrastructure resource: Sharepoint
- Infrastructure resource: Database

- Infrastructure resource: Licences
- Infrastructure resource: institutional repository
- Infrastructure resource: Archive
- Additional infrastructure resources required: [FREETEXT]
- The usual workplace infrastructure resources are sufficient.
- Human resources through consultation and/or training by NFDI4Chem and/or the FDM team at your university or research institution
- Personnel effort provided by the institute in person-months: [FREETEXT]
- Personnel effort in the project in person-months: [FREETEXT]
- Other: [FREETEXT]